

Model predictive manhole traversal with LiDAR-based view synthesis

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Abstract—Autonomous inspection of maritime vessels using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles can prove difficult due to low light conditions, minimum space and battery limitations. This paper proposes a strategy for optimized manhole traversal in the scenario of maritime vessel ballast tank inspection. A dense point cloud, collected during the exploration of the ballast tank, is used to localize the manhole that the UAV has to traverse through. The prediction of the manhole is performed on synthesized 360° panoramic views of the point cloud, originating from positions inside the mapped area. This manhole prediction enables a Model Predictive Control framework to find the optimal path through the manhole, taking into account the capabilities of the UAV and the topological constraints of the confined space. The manhole localization method is able to predict the center of the manhole with an average success rate of 89.6%, which can be raised to 94% after the ensembling of multiple predictions from different assumed camera positions. Simulated results show the robustness of the Model Predictive Control method in a wide array of different scenarios. We demonstrate the ability of the method to predict accurately the manhole and efficiently pass through it using a UAV, in a real-world experimental setup.

Index Terms—Optimal control, UAV, Manhole, Confined Spaces

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, researchers and companies have invested in robotics solutions to automate inspection and surveillance processes across multiple industries [1]–[3]. The prioritisation of the processes to be automated is defined by cost, risk and regulations. The inspection of maritime vessel ballast tanks is a challenging and

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Fig. 1: Depiction of a quadcopter inspecting a replica ballast tank in experimental setup.

dangerous process that has been selected as a candidate for automation [4].

Ballast tanks have to be manually inspected periodically for structural degradation issues. They are comprised of compartments that are connected through elliptical holes, called "manholes". Inspectors have to traverse through manholes from the first compartment to the last, in low to no light conditions, to identify the structural integrity of the tanks. Depending on the cargo type and the usage of inert gas, this is a hazardous operation that can endanger the life of the surveyors and crew. Additionally, this operation can be lengthy, costing the vessel owners a significant amount of money. This can be solved by autonomously inspecting the tanks using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) [5]–[7].

In this paper, we present a system for autonomous UAV traversal of manholes between ballast tank compartments. After the UAV finishes the exploration of

a compartment, it tries to identify the manhole to be used to enter the next compartment employing a dense point cloud that was collected during the exploration. To accelerate processing, the point cloud is transformed into panoramic 360° images. Each image is used to identify the manholes of the ballast tank, based on the reprojection of the center of the detected ellipse and the plane the manhole is located on. The best prediction is then used by a Model Predictive Control (MPC) controller, that identifies the optimal path from the current position to the next compartment (i.e. a fixed-distance point past the manhole.).

The main contributions of the paper are:

- A novel manhole localization method that uses the information of dense point clouds and can run onboard UAVs,
- An MPC controller for optimal manhole traversal,
- Real life experiments of a drone flying through a narrow manhole autonomously.

II. RELATED WORK

UAVs have been used for a wide range of tasks, including mapping [8]–[10], inspection [11]–[15], search and rescue operations [16]–[18]. They provide ease of traversal through cluttered spaces, invariant to ground conditions [19]. In the context of autonomous ballast tank inspection, UAVs must travel to each ballast tank compartment while passing through narrow manholes. In the past, there have a number of works in the literature that have researched the topic of manhole traversal.

In [20], a collision resilient UAV is used to pass through rectangular manhole openings. A monochromatic stereo image pair is used to detect the manhole. After a series of morphological operations on the images, closed contours are chosen and filtered based on their shape. The position of the manhole is calculated based on the disparity values of the chosen contour. In contrast, we use 3D LiDAR data to create 360° panoramic images based on different assumed camera positions, making our approach more adaptable, and invariant to the current position of the UAV.

In [21], the authors use a depth-based deep learning approach to detect the manholes. The proposed model utilizes depth images to predict the position of the manhole. Then, the UAV aligns with the hole before flying perpendicularly through it. In our proposed detection method, we use 3D LiDAR data to not only detect the manhole, but localize it with respect to the odometry frame of the UAV.

In [22], 3D LiDAR data are used to detect and localize the manhole that the UAV will traverse through. Two points are selected in the current and next ballast tank compartments, whose connecting line passes perpendicularly through the center of the hole. Then, an integrated

planner creates the path that the UAV has to follow to pass through the manhole. We use an MPC-based approach, to create an optimal path from the current to the next ballast tank compartment.

III. MANHOLE DETECTION

The first step in manhole traversal is to detect and localize the hole that the UAV has to go through.

A. Point cloud to panoramic image generation

In this paper, we use the dense point cloud representation of the ballast tank that is collected with a LiDAR during exploration. Methods that utilize dense point clouds, tend to be computationally expensive, and generally not likely to run onboard UAVs. To solve this issue, we transform the point cloud into a panoramic 360° image.

The process starts by assuming a camera sensor at the mean of the points in the dense point cloud. Then, we calculate the relative positions for all points to the assumed camera sensor, create a unit directional vector for each point, and calculate its spherical coordinates. We calculate the equirectangular pixel mapping, so that:

$$u = \frac{\theta + \pi}{2\pi} c_w, \quad (1a)$$

$$v = \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \phi}{\pi} c_h, \quad (1b)$$

where θ, ϕ is the horizontal and vertical angles around the camera axes, and c_w, c_h are the width and height of the produced image. For each pixel, we calculate which point is closest to the assumed camera sensor. The relative distance of the point closest to the camera is used as the pixel value. The last step is to normalize the pixel values to the $[0, 255]$ range. Pixels that no points are projected onto get the max value of the range.

The hole detection method will fail if the hole is "cropped" by the edges of the produced image. We tackle this problem by padding the edges of the image with its other side counterparts, potentially creating two identical holes at the edge of the image. It doesn't matter which of the two identical holes we detect, since they represent the projections of the same points on the image plane.

B. Detection

After we produce the image representation of the point cloud, we apply classical computer vision methods to detect the center of the hole. The denser the point cloud is, the less black pixels the image has at the areas that represent holes. To fill the wall information but keep the holes, we apply morphological operations to the image. Then, we use Canny edge detection to find the contours of the image, and we fit an ellipse to each contour. If the fitted ellipse satisfies the eccentricity and solidity

(a) Original 360° image generated from the LiDAR. Note that the image is padded to avoid edge cases.

(b) Predicted manhole.

(c) Clustered manhole points in point cloud. Green points belong to the manhole and red points to the next ballast tank compartment.

(d) Predicted center of manhole. The predicted center is shown in orange, the camera position in magenta and the points used for the plane fitting process in green.

Fig. 2: The four steps in the manhole detection process.

requirements for a manhole, we add it to a valid set of ellipses.

The pixels of the ellipse boundaries correspond to points in the point cloud that in part belong to the wall around the manhole, and in part to points in the next ballast tank compartment. We use DBSCAN [23] to cluster the points between the two, and calculate the size of each clustered point cloud, to determine which points can belong to a manhole. Observing the clustered point clouds in 3D, the points belonging to the next ballast tank compartment create a distorted 3D manhole that has greater size than the actual one, so they are eliminated.

The next step is to estimate the plane of the wall that the manhole is located on. To do so, we select a subset of the pointcloud. Its center is the center of the manhole points cluster and the selected points are points in the original point cloud in a 0.7 meter radius from the center. Then, we use RANSAC [24] to fit a plane on those points. We predict the center of the manhole the intersection of the ray from the camera position to the center of the ellipse in the image, and the plane we predicted. Lastly, we remove predictions that lie near the previously detected manhole, so that the UAV does not move to a past explored compartment. The detection steps can be seen in Figure 2.

IV. OPTIMAL MANHOLE TRAVERSAL

In this section, we discuss the control method designed for UAV manhole traversal. We define the manhole traversal problem in an MPC control paradigm. For the purpose of simplification, the optimization problem is defined in the manhole frame of reference, which is located at the center of the manhole. The y, z axis are perpendicular to the plane of the hole, and the x axis is pointing towards the next ballast tank compartment. This can be seen in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: This figure shows the manhole frame of reference used for the MPC problem formulation. The x, y, z axes are represented by red, green and blue, respectively.

A. System dynamics

The UAV prediction model is based on the Euler single particle kinematics equations. The UAV dynamics are modeled as a discrete linear time-invariant system in the form:

$$x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k, \quad (2)$$

where the state vector $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^6$ consists of positions and velocities in three dimensions, and the control input $u_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the accelerations. The system matrices are given by:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} I_{3 \times 3} & I_{3 \times 3} \Delta t \\ 0_{3 \times 3} & I_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} I_{3 \times 3} \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \\ I_{3 \times 3} \Delta t \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $I_{3 \times 3}$ is the identity matrix, and Δt is the sampling time.

B. MPC objective function

With the dynamic formulation shown above, we can formulate the MPC optimization problem for manhole traversal. We try to minimize the error to the target position inside the next ballast tank compartment, without violating the velocity and acceleration constraints of the UAV, and the manhole constraint. The manhole constraint is defined as a position elliptical constraint that is only taken into account when the UAV is close to the wall of the ballast tank. The optimization problem is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\{u_k\}_{k=0}^{N-1}} & \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} [(x_k - x_{\text{target}})^\top Q (x_k - x_{\text{target}}) + u_k^\top R u_k] \\ \text{s.t.} & \quad x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ & \quad |u_k| \leq u_{\text{max}}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ & \quad |\alpha_k| \leq \alpha_{\text{max}}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N \\ & \quad \left(\frac{y_k - c_y}{a_{\text{eff}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{z_k - c_z}{b_{\text{eff}}} \right)^2 \leq 1, \\ & \quad \text{for } |x_k - x_{\text{wall}}| < \delta, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where x_{target} is the target state, Q, R are the state and control weight matrices, u_{max} and α_{max} are the maximum velocities and accelerations, $[c_y, c_z]$ is the center of the ellipse, a_{eff} and b_{eff} are the semi-major and semi-minor axes of the ellipse, and δ is the distance from the wall that the ellipse constraint is enforced. For the purpose of the hole passing problem, the target state is always:

$$x_{\text{target}} = [1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]^\top. \quad (6)$$

We consider that the UAV has to reach one meter inside the ballast tank with no velocity. The dynamics constraint enforces the system evolution for the optimization problem. Velocity and acceleration limits have to be enforced with hard constraints, so that the optimization problem does not produce unreachable states. The ellipse constraint makes sure that the UAV will pass through the manhole to reach the target position. We note here that the ellipse used for the position constraint is not a fitted ellipse on the manhole boundary, but a small ellipse at the center of the manhole, so that there is enough clearance between the UAV and the manhole edges.

C. Optimization fallback

The optimization problem can potentially fail to find solutions. This can happen due to the scale of the problem, infeasible constraints, MPC horizon, etc. In the case of this MPC problem formulation, we have designed a fallback mechanism that utilizes a PID controller to navigate the UAV to a feasible state whenever the MPC optimization problem fails.

The PID controller is designed to track the error of the UAV state to a predefined target state. The fallback target state is:

$$x_{\text{fallback}} = [-1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]^\top. \quad (7)$$

We define the fallback position as the one-meter z offset to the center of the ellipse in the hole frame. The closer the UAV is with regards to the theoretical center line passing perpendicularly through the center of the ellipse, the easier it is for the MPC controller to find an optimal solution.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we discuss the simulated and experimental results for the described methods. We validate individually the detection and control methods using simulated data, and show that our method can be effectively used for UAV manhole traversal in real-world conditions.

A. Manhole detection ablation study

The performance of the manhole detection method depends on the assumed camera sensor position. In order to evaluate the performance of the method for different camera positions, we artificially created a point cloud of a $1.5 \times 1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ m}^3$ cube with a 0.6×0.4 elliptical hole on one of its sides, with added noise. We then chose positions in a $1 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ m}^3$ similarly centered cube.

The ablation study results can be seen in Figure 4a. We assume that the method is successful if it predicts the center of the hole with an error of less than 0.1 meters. The method is able to successfully predict the

(a) Heatmap of success rate of the manhole detection method based on the hole-camera relative angle.

(b) Heatmap of success rate of the manhole detection method based on the hole-camera relative angle, filtered to remove cases with more than 1.5 meter errors.

(c) Heatmap of detection error of the manhole detection method based on the hole-camera relative angle, filtered to remove cases with more than 1.5 meter errors.

Fig. 4: Ablation study for the manhole detection method.

center of the hole 89.6% of the times. Camera positions that are more aligned with the horizon of the manhole provide more consistent results than positions that are to the edges of the hole.

During our testing, we observed that most of the failed cases were providing predictions that had errors much higher than 2 meters, which can be easily detected and filtered out. In Figures 4b, 4c, we filtered the results and removed all errors that are higher than 1.5 meters. The

method in this case had a success rate of 94.2%.

The solution to the outliers problem is to run the method for different camera positions close to the mean of the point cloud. The method can run onboard the UAV in a fraction of a second, making it possible to run it multiple times and use only the mean of the inlier predictions that lie close to each other.

B. MPC evaluation

In this subsection we discuss the performance of the MPC control manhole traversal paradigm. For our simulated UAV, we used a maximum acceleration of $2m/s^2$. For the MPC parameters, we used position weight $q_{pos} = 20$, velocity weight $q_{vel} = 5$, and control weight $r_{ctrl} = 0.02$. The MPC controller runs at $10Hz$ with a horizon of 10 steps. The effective ellipse is defined as described in IV-B, with semi-major and semi-minor axes of $0.05m$. For the evaluation, we conducted 500 experiments for each different maximum UAV velocity. The results of the experiments are shown in table I.

TABLE I: Summary of Manhole Passing Metrics

v_{max} (m/s)	d_w (m)	h_d (m)	Success (%)
0.2	0.4900	0.00023 ± 0.00013	100.0
0.5	0.3714	0.01617 ± 0.01310	100.0
1.0	0.2599	0.03330 ± 0.01774	96.2
2.0	0.0533	0.03484 ± 0.01578	90.6
5.0	0.0364	0.03544 ± 0.01460	89.0
10.0	0.0364	0.03556 ± 0.01463	89.0

Lower maximum velocities show increased tracking and success rates. As the maximum velocity increases, the success rate of the proposed method is reduced, and the probability of the UAV colliding with the perimeter of the manhole is higher. In our experiments, we observe that the optimization limits the UAV speed to be less than $3m/s$ in all cases, so velocities equal or higher than that produce similar results.

C. Real-world testing

Real-world tests were performed to validate the system in real life conditions. In Figure 5, we show the results of a test flight using a replica ballast tank, also seen in Figure 1. We have removed points of the point cloud that are not close to the trajectory of the UAV for clarity. The Flyability Elios 3 quadcopter was used for the testing. We validate that the MPC method can produce an optimal trajectory for passing through the manhole and that the UAV is then able to follow it.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a system for systematically detecting elliptical manholes between ballast tank compartments, and a strategy to optimally traverse through them. The approach has the advantage of processing dense

Fig. 5: Results from test flight using the MPC method. The blue sphere represents the start point, the transform frame shows the detected center and the red sphere represents the end goal. The path the UAV followed is shown in green.

point cloud data in a computer vision framework fast and robustly, while disregarding the current position of the UAV, to localize the next manhole the UAV has to traverse. The drone trajectory through the manhole is then calculated by an MPC framework that takes into consideration the limitations of the UAV and the topological specifications of the hole. Our results show that the method can be used onboard a UAV to complete the task of manhole traversal efficiently.

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